

STUDY OF THE THERMAL PROPERTIES OF STARCH-BASED BIOPOLYMERS CONTAINING SILICON

M.T. Karshiev¹, F.N. Nurkulov²

DSc Doctoral Candidate at Qarshi State University¹

Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor. Tashkent Chemical and Technological Scientific
Research Institute²

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Abstract. *This article is aimed at studying the thermal and mechanical properties of reinforced materials. Various formulations based on the structure of plasticized starch were realized, in which the fibre length and nature were varied by incorporating additives into the formulation. Starch fibers exhibiting non-uniform surface tension were tested. Following the extrusion and injection processes, the properties of the maize starch-based biocomposites were analyzed. Mechanical properties (tensile tests), thermo-mechanical properties (DTA), and thermal degradation (TGA) were analyzed. These results are consistent with static mechanical behaviour, which showed that the addition of a filler (up to 30-40%) improves the thermal resistance of these biocomposites.*

Keywords: *silicon starch biopolymer, plasticised starch, thermo-mechanical properties, surface tension, thermal stability, extrusion method.*

Introduction. In recent years, a rapid growth has occurred in the consumption of fibre reinforced polymer composites, yielding a unique combination of high performance, great versatility and processing advantages at a favourable cost. Among other fillers used for such polymeric products, cellulose fibres (CF) became an important class of reinforcing materials. They show many advantages, including low density, little damage during processing, little requirements on processing equipment, biodegradability, high stiffness and relatively low price [1],[2],[3]. However, the main disadvantage of cellulose filled polymer composites seems to be the incompatibility between the hydrophilic cellulose fibres and the hydrophobic thermoplastic (particularly, polyolefin) matrix. This may contribute to a poor stress transfer between the matrix and the filler, and a limited fibre dispersion in thermoplastic melt, leading to unsatisfactory final properties of the materials produced [4],[5],[6]. As a result, research efforts have been focused to find suitable coupling agents in the area of wood and cellulose reinforced thermoplastic composites, in order to overcome the problems mentioned [7],[8]. Effects of the interfacial adhesion on the morphological characteristics and corresponding physical properties have been studied. Among other additives used for surface treatment and compatibilizing, maleic anhydride grafted polyethylene (MAPE) has been found very efficient in improving the filler dispersion and the compatibility in PE–CF composites[9]. The aim of this work is the study of the morphology, thermal, and viscoelastic behaviour of isotactic PE reinforced with two types of cellulose fillers (short- and micro-fibres), and a small weight percentage of MAPE compatibilizer. Experiments are performed by means of dynamic mechanical thermoanalysis (DMTA), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), polarization light microscopy and X-ray diffraction. Investigations on the structural and physical behaviour of drawn composites is an

important part of the work. These studies provide valuable insights into the relationship between the properties of the composites considered in both isotropic and oriented states[10].

Laboratory-synthesised Si-NaKMK was used to modify biodegradable polymer composites based on sodium carboxymethyl starch. For the experiment, polyethylene F-0220, Si-NaKMK and starch were used in specific ratios of 1:0.4 and 1:0.5, and the components were mixed in a mechanical autoclave for 90 minutes at a temperature of 150-160°C. The resulting composition was extruded into granules.

During the experiment, the parameters of the IR spectrum were analysed to study the physicochemical properties of the composition of the synthesised polyethylene, Si-NaKMK and starch. In the next stage, pellets were prepared from the obtained granules for analysis at a temperature of 170-175°C.

The interaction between the starch granule surface and the silicon compound occurs through three different binding mechanisms:

1. Hydrogen bonding:

2. Covalent bonding: (etherification)

$\Delta H^\circ = -15 \text{ kJ/mol}$, $E_a = 85 \text{ kJ/mol}$, $T > 60^\circ\text{C}$

3. Electrostatic interaction (when APTES is utilized):

The type and amount of bond formed depend on the synthesis conditions—pH, temperature, ratios, and time. For covalent bonding, the temperature must exceed 60 °C and the pH must be in the range of 4–7. Under these conditions, silicon compounds can also enter the amylose spiral, forming inclusion complexes.

A first-order equation describes the reaction kinetics, and the activation energy lies in the range EA = 75–95 kJ/mol. An increase in temperature of 10°C approximately doubles the reaction rate (according to the Arrhenius equation).

Thermal analysis. The following TGA-SDTA analysis results for starch and Si-NaKMK are presented, which show that the thermal decomposition process of starch and Si-NaKMK can be divided into three stages.

Figure 1. TGA/SDTA curves of Si-NaKMK.

In the first stage, physically adsorbed water and chemically bonded water are released from the structure at 16.57–196.43 °C, as evidenced by the descending section of the curve. During this interval, the mass loss of Si-NaKMK is 1.445 mg (14.67 %), the time taken for decomposition is 19.30 minutes, and in starch the mass loss during the first stage, between 25.35 and 266 °C, is 0.969 mg. (12.32%), time taken 25.38 minutes; Second stage, the macromolecular glycosidic bonds in the structure of Si-NaKMK, C-O and C-C bonds are cleaved, forming new products at 196.43–409.73°C; this is a rapid weight loss stage with a weight loss rate of approximately 54.1%, In starch, this process accounted for 73.9% of the weight loss at 266–413 °C. In the third stage, at temperatures above 409.73–601 °C, the residual part of the product begins to convert into aromatic ring compounds, then gradually forms a graphitic structure. In this temperature range, the weight loss was 1.734 mg (17.6%), whereas in the starch it was 0.304 mg (3.8%) at 413–601 °C (Figure 1).

From the results of the analysis presented, it can be seen from the second-stage decomposition curves that starch is thermally more unstable than Si-NaKMK: at 410 °C, starch loses 73.9% of its weight, whereas Si-NaKMK loses 54%. This indicates the thermal stability of Si-NaKMK (Figure 1).

Figure 2. TGA/SDTA curves of starch.

Table 1.

DTA analysis of sodium carboxymethyl starch with silicon.

№	dw 9.84	1/T	dw/dt	M.r	Минт	T ⁰ +K
1	8.99	0.0026	0.097	0.85	8.7	373
2	8.41	0.0021	0.076	1.43	18.7	473
3	4.54	0.0017	0.184	5.3	28.7	573
4	3.22	0.0014	0.171	6.62	38.68	673
5	2.18	0.0012	0.150	7.3	48.66	773
6	1.42	0.0011	0.143	8.42	58.7	873
7	1.32	0.0011	0.140	8.52	60.6	892

Mechanical tests. The mechanical strength parameters were determined by stretching the specimens on an ISO-527-2019 compliant (RM-50 with Stretch Test software) universal testing machine (Table 3). The physical and mechanical properties were determined on an AGS-X 10 kN tensile machine (Japan) under uniaxial tension at a strain rate of 10 mm/min and a load of 100 N.

The tensile strength was determined from the obtained data. For the specimens obtained, the defining mechanical properties are the tensile force, the elongation at break and the modulus of elasticity, all of which are relative.

Table 2.

TGA analysis of sodium carboxymethyl starch

N _o	D _w 9.84	Ln(W ₁ /W ₂)	1/T *10 ⁻³
1	8.99	0.089	2.6
2	8.41	0.156	2.1
3	4.54	0.774	1.7
4	3.22	1.117	1.4
5	2.18	1.509	1.2
6	1.42	1.937	1.1
7	1.32	0.125	1.1

Within the range where there is a balance between elasticity and strength, the higher one of these parameters, the lower the other. Thus, the samples with a PE:Si-NaKMK (60:40) ratio exhibit the best elasticity but the lowest strength, whereas the PE:Si-NaKMK (70:30) sample, conversely, shows the highest tensile strength.

The results presented in Table 3 are for the polymer samples obtained by modifying the polyethylene polymer with the Si-NaKMK synthesised during the experiment, When comparing their mechanical properties with those of the PHA/10-PM biopolymer, the figures in the table can be observed.

Table 3.

Mechanical properties of modified polyethylene and the analogue

Composition of the samples	Tensile force (N)	Elongation (mm)	Breaking force (MPa)	Deformation %
PHA/10-PM (an)	70N	30	5,5	106 %
PE:Si-NaKMK (70:30)	105N	120	7,7	400 %
PE+Si-NaKMK (60:40)	97N	110	6,6	360 %
PE+Si-NaKNK (50:50)	82N	52	6,5	160 %

These polymer samples contain up to 50% modified silicon carboxy-starch. If the physical-mechanical properties of the resulting polymer composition are examined, its overall mechanical properties are superior to those of the analogous compositions. The results show that, compared with control samples, the deformation–strength parameters of the extrusion-processed polymer films are higher than those of the analogues. The mechanical performance data of the polymer samples obtained in the experiment are presented in Table 3.

The product yield is 75–92%, while the silicon bonding degree is 15–35%. The method is economically favourable for industrial-scale production and enables the production of large batches.

Conclusion. Various formulations based on a plasticised starch chain were developed, with the structure formula (Sodium metasilicate/starch ratio = 0.259 and 0.537), and fibre length (from 50 µm to 1 mm), filler content (up to 40%) and the nature of the fibres varied. The fibres exhibit clear surface tension, with the native starch fibres being more polar than the modified starch fibres. Compared to neat starch, DTA analysis shows some significant changes in the peak reaction

temperature in these biocomposites, which may be related to the following. The bonding in the starch–silica system occurs through three mechanisms: hydrogen bonds (10–30 kJ/mol), covalent Si–O–C bonds (EA = 75–95 kJ/mol), and electrostatic interactions (in the APTES system). Covalent bonds are the primary factor for thermal and mechanical stability. Increasing the silicon content from 10% to 40% increases the mechanical strength from 6,5 to 7,7 MPa and the thermal stability from 413°C to 601°C.

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